

THE IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN ENHANCING READING SKILLS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly being integrated into foreign language learning, revolutionizing traditional approaches, particularly in enhancing reading skills. AI-driven tools offer personalized learning experiences, adaptive content, and real-time feedback, tailored to meet individual learners' needs. This article examines the significance of reading skills in language acquisition, the role of AI in improving these skills, and the challenges associated with AI-assisted language learning. The discussion also explores future directions, suggesting that while AI has the potential to transform language education, its full capabilities remain underutilized.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, foreign language learning, reading skills, adaptive learning, ai in education.

Artificial Intelligence has become a transformative force in education, with its applications in language learning attracting significant interest (Iqbal et al., 2024). Language acquisition is a multifaceted process that requires the mastery of various skills, including reading, which is foundational for developing other linguistic abilities such as writing and speaking (Hung & Ngan, 2015). AI's role in enhancing reading skills is particularly noteworthy as it offers innovative solutions that address individual learning challenges and improve overall language proficiency (Fattah et al., 2023).

Reading is a critical component of language acquisition, enabling learners to access a vast array of texts that enhance vocabulary, comprehension, and cultural understanding (Celik & Altun, 2023). In the context of foreign language learning, proficiency in reading allows learners to engage deeply with the language, facilitating immersion and better retention (Celik & Altun, 2023). However, many learners struggle with reading in a new language due to unfamiliar syntax, vocabulary, and cultural references (Davoudi & Yousefi, 2015). Therefore, effective strategies and tools that aid in developing reading skills are crucial for successful language acquisition.

AI offers a variety of tools and technologies that can significantly enhance reading skills in foreign language learners:

- Natural Language Processing (NLP) Applications: NLP algorithms analyze text to assess readability, provide contextual definitions, and suggest synonyms or translations, helping learners understand material more effectively (Bengoetxea et al., 2020).
- Adaptive Learning Systems: These systems tailor reading materials to the learner's proficiency level, gradually increasing complexity as skills improve (Azoulay et al., 2020). AI analyzes progress and adjusts content, ensuring learners remain engaged and challenged.

- Text-to-Speech (TTS) Technology: TTS tools read aloud text, aiding learners with pronunciation and auditory comprehension (Gomes et al., 2018; Gottardi et al., 2022). This technology is especially beneficial for beginners who struggle with new word pronunciation.
- Automated Feedback and Assessment: AI-powered platforms offer immediate feedback on reading comprehension exercises, identifying areas of difficulty and providing suggestions for improvement (Redhu et al., 2024). This enables real-time adjustments, fostering more efficient learning.

Despite the advantages of AI in enhancing reading skills, several challenges persist:

1. Over-reliance on AI: There is a risk of reduced human interaction, which is crucial for developing conversational and contextual language skills (Rebolledo Font de la Vall & González Araya, 2023).
2. Quality of AI Data: The effectiveness of AI tools often depends on the quality of the data they are trained on, which may not fully represent the diversity of languages and cultures (Rebolledo Font de la Vall & González Araya, 2023).
3. Privacy and Ethical Concerns: The use of AI in education raises issues related to data security and the potential for biased algorithms, which could impact the fairness and accessibility of language learning tools (Rebolledo Font de la Vall & González Araya, 2023).

The future of AI in language learning lies in developing more sophisticated and culturally aware systems that provide personalized and immersive experiences (Rebolledo Font de la Vall & González Araya, 2023). Collaboration among educators, linguists, and AI developers will be essential to overcome current limitations and fully harness AI's potential in language education. Continued research and investment in AI technologies are crucial to creating tools that are not only effective but also accessible and equitable for all learners.

AI's integration into foreign language learning has the potential to significantly enhance reading skills, offering personalized, adaptive, and efficient learning experiences. However, the successful implementation of AI in this domain requires careful consideration of its challenges, including over-reliance on technology, data quality, and ethical concerns. As AI continues to evolve, its role in language education will likely expand, offering new opportunities for learners to achieve proficiency in foreign languages. Balancing technological innovation with the preservation of essential educational values will be key to realizing the full benefits of AI in language learning.

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